

Youth policy in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: The wings of the future, which occupy an important place in the life of our country and people, are young people. Therefore, every state and country creates its own legal framework for youth policy, thereby taking measures to create great opportunities and conditions for them. This article provides a brief analysis of the legal documents adopted for youth in our country and their brief analysis of such relations.

Key words: youth policy, youth support, Youth 2030,

In our country, the issue of youth is one of the most important areas of state policy. 2024 was announced by the head of our country as the year of «Supporting youth and business».

Important reforms carried out in our country in recent years had a great impact on young people, their life positions, goals and aspirations. Currently, 60% of the population is under 30 years of age in Uzbekistan. This share is expected to increase further in the next decade and reach its highest point by 2045, which will further increase the urgency of well-thought-out public policies regarding youth. Undoubtedly, the leading positions in the implementation of reforms in the political, economic and social spheres belong to the youth. For this reason, the task of forming a high sense of high humanity, patriotism and protection of youth in society is urgent. Therefore, the solution of this task is directly related to the processes and events taking place in our society and state, taking into account all the factors affecting

today's youth, including economic, political, moral, moral and other factors. will need to be considered. The UN «Youth 2030» strategy specifically states that youth is an extremely valuable and important resource (wealth), and the money spent on them pays off several times over. Taking this into account, the main areas (education, employment and other areas) that the countries of the world need to pay active and consistent attention to the UN Sustainable Development Goals have been defined. Today, a legal and institutional framework aimed at ensuring the implementation of the state policy on youth has been created in Uzbekistan. The Youth Affairs Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan is working, an interdepartmental council on youth issues has been formed under the chairmanship of the Prime Minister of our country. Under the agency, the Foundation for the support of the state policy on youth, as well as the Institute for the study of youth problems and the training of promising young people were established. A commission on youth issues was established in the Legislative Chamber of our Parliament, «Youth Day» is celebrated in Uzbekistan on June 30, 2017, this holiday is a database «Youth Register» for identifying, solving and monitoring official youth problems in our country. it is worth noting that the introduction of the «Brave boy award, the establishment of the medal of the creator of the future», and the opening of funds to support youth initiatives. 12 million young men and women were covered within the framework of the «Five Initiatives Olympiad» project. 623 sports grounds were built in the neighborhoods for young people who were winners and prize-winners of the project. In 2023, the types of assistance provided through the «Youth Register» system will increase to 30 The period for reviewing applications has been reduced from 30 days to 5 days. provided for. Even today, there are many opportunities and conditions created by the leader of our country for our youth. Full development of young people, protection of their rights, creation of various opportunities by the state for underprivileged young people,

including: allocation of subsidies for them, access to more than 30 opportunities for persons on the «Youth Register», and benefits given by the state for housing. It is a clear example of the policy of Uzbekistan, which looks at young people with great confidence.

The «Bozatov Fest» festival, which is held every year in the Bozatov district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan on the initiative of our head of state Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, to identify talented young people, also introduces talented young artists to our country and provides them with material and moral support from the state. It is no exaggeration to say that he is showing his great help in giving. The privileges and conditions mentioned above are a clear example of the paternal love of the head of our state towards our youth.

A number of decisions are being taken by our government to support the youth in our country. This initiative is aimed at expanding the opportunities of young people, increasing their activity and socio-economic development.

- «Youth is the key to success» program allows young people to develop leadership skills, participate in community service and prepare for the labor market.
- «My profession is my future» initiative supports vocational training and employment opportunities for young people.
- Youth Housing This program provides affordable housing solutions for young families and individuals.
- «Youth Innovation Ideas» (Youth Innovation Ideas): This initiative encourages and supports youth entrepreneurship and innovation.

The implementation of youth policy in Uzbekistan is controlled by relevant state bodies, including the Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports. Youth organizations,

non-governmental non-profit organizations and international partners also contribute to policy support and evaluation of its effectiveness.

Despite the government's efforts, there are still challenges in the implementation of youth policies, including:

Opportunities for education and employment of young people in rural areas are limited in some places.

Despite this, Uzbekistan has made significant progress in meeting the needs of the youth of its population and is committed to improving their well-being and future prospects.

In conclusion, Youth Policy is very important for the activity of young people in Uzbekistan, to hear their opinions, to see their proposals and to get them a good profession. They are of great importance in the development of the country, and efforts are being made to implement their wishes and ideas and to develop their potential and skills.

Today's youth are the future of our country, they must make a great contribution to the prosperity of our country. After all, young people are one of the positive forces that have unlimited potential to contribute to social development and progress in society. For this reason, the democratic values that are just budding in Uzbekistan are being most actively absorbed by young people. It gives hope that the new generation will lead the country based on modern methods, perspectives and values.

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